

Roles of Public Library Information Services in Promoting Entrepreneurship, Fostering Innovation, Enhancing Capacity Building and Advancing Global Sustainability in Northwest Nigeria

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Abstract

Public libraries have progressively evolved from simple repositories of books into dynamic institutions that promote entrepreneurship, innovation, capacity building, and sustainable development. In Northwest Nigeria, where socio-economic issues such as unemployment, poverty, low literacy rates, and limited access to technology persist, public libraries are strategically positioned to close gaps and drive progress. This study explores the role of public library information services in supporting entrepreneurship, fostering innovation, strengthening capacity building, and advancing the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in the region. Guided by four research questions, a descriptive survey design was employed, with data analysed using mean scores, correlations, and regression analyses. Results indicate that public libraries play a significant role in entrepreneurship and innovation, mainly by providing access to business information and ICT tools, although their involvement in specialised entrepreneurial training remains limited. Digital literacy efforts are notably robust within capacity-building initiatives. Libraries' contributions to the SDGs are most apparent in education and employment-related goals, while their influence on environmental awareness is comparatively modest. Key challenges identified include insufficient funding, poor ICT infrastructure, and limited policy support. Correlation and regression analyses suggest that entrepreneurship, innovation, and capacity building are strong predictors of libraries' contributions to the SDGs, with capacity building emerging as the most influential factor. The study concludes that public libraries in Northwest Nigeria are essential agents of socio-economic change but require greater institutional backing. It recommends increased funding, enhanced ICT integration, stronger policy recognition, and strategic partnerships to optimise their impact on entrepreneurship, innovation, and sustainable development.

Keywords: Public Library, Information Services, Entrepreneurship, Innovation, Capacity Building, Sustainable Development Goals

Introduction

Public libraries, once seen mainly as repositories of books and reading materials, have transformed into vibrant institutions offering diverse information services tailored to their communities' needs. In the 21st century, their role has grown beyond promoting literacy to include entrepreneurship development, innovation support, capacity building, and sustainable development. In developing countries like

Nigeria—especially in the Northwest region—public libraries are strategically placed to bridge knowledge gaps, reduce inequalities, and stimulate local growth through equitable access to information and services. Libraries act as essential tools for societal progress. To enable individuals to live responsibly and productively, libraries must be responsive to their needs and provide prompt access to relevant information. As Okoro, Akidi, and Arua (2014) state, public libraries should offer services that foster entrepreneurship, support innovation, enhance capacity building, and promote the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Likewise, Oladokun, Yemi-Peters, and Owolabi underline that the primary function of libraries is to deliver information to their communities. The acquisition of knowledge dispels ignorance; therefore, the main goal of the library is to serve as a hub where individuals can access the knowledge they need to reduce uncertainty and gain a better understanding of their environment.

The Northwest region of Nigeria—comprising Jigawa, Kaduna, Kano, Katsina, Kebbi, Sokoto, and Zamfara States—faces ongoing socio-economic challenges, including high unemployment, low literacy levels, widespread poverty, and limited access to global opportunities. In this context, public libraries can serve as catalysts for entrepreneurial growth by providing access to relevant information resources, training programmes, and environments that foster creativity and innovation. This study examines the diverse role of public library information services in encouraging entrepreneurship, promoting innovation, strengthening capacity building, and supporting global sustainability. It focuses particularly on the challenges and opportunities faced by public libraries in Northwest Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Despite the recognised importance of public libraries in national development, their role in promoting entrepreneurship, innovation, capacity building, and sustainable development in Nigeria remains underexplored and underutilised. The Northwest zone of Nigeria continues to face significant socio-economic challenges, including high unemployment, widespread poverty, limited access to ICT facilities, and inadequate opportunities for capacity development. Although public libraries have the potential to drive economic empowerment and innovation, many are hampered by insufficient funding, poor infrastructure, inadequate staffing, and a lack of government support.

Globally, there is growing recognition of libraries as strategic partners in achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). However, in Northwest Nigeria, the extent to which public library services contribute to goals such as quality education, gender equality, and the reduction of inequalities remains poorly documented. This lack of empirical knowledge raises important questions: Are public libraries in Northwest Nigeria effectively supporting entrepreneurship and innovation? To what degree are they building community capacity? What challenges hinder them from fulfilling their developmental role? Addressing these questions is vital to reimagining the role of public libraries in the region's socio-economic transformation.

Objectives

This study aims to achieve the following objectives:

1. To examine how public libraries contribute to entrepreneurial development and innovation among users in Northwest Nigeria.

2. To assess the extent to which public libraries engage in capacity building for knowledge and skill acquisition.
3. To evaluate the impact of public library initiatives on achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).
4. To identify the challenges hindering public library information services in fostering innovation, enhancing capacity building, and advancing global sustainability.

Hypotheses

- **H₀₁:** Library services (entrepreneurship, innovation, and capacity building) do not significantly predict the impact of public libraries on SDG-related outcomes.
- **H₀₂:** There is no significant relationship between library services (entrepreneurship, innovation, capacity building, and SDGs) and user outcomes.

Literature Review

Public libraries are vital community institutions that offer free access to information and knowledge, positioning them as key contributors to sustainable development. They function as hubs for learning, innovation, and collaboration, and play a significant role in raising awareness and understanding of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (Kosciejew, 2020; Panda & Das, 2022). With a longstanding history of promoting literacy, education, and equitable access to information, libraries are well-equipped to support the SDGs through their resources, expertise, and outreach initiatives. Several studies affirm that public libraries are strategically positioned to advance the SDGs (Omona, 2020; Panda & Das, 2022; Popoola, 2019). They do so by providing access to relevant information, facilitating educational programs, and fostering community engagement. Libraries also contribute through targeted programming, specialised services, and partnerships with stakeholders across sectors.

In the realm of entrepreneurship, public libraries play a crucial role by offering access to business information, market intelligence, and digital tools. Aina (2019) describes libraries as knowledge hubs where entrepreneurs can obtain business plans, feasibility studies, and innovation toolkits. Research in Africa (Nwalo & Oyedokun, 2020) highlights how library services help reduce information barriers that hinder small-scale business development. Innovation thrives on creativity, experimentation, and access to information. Public libraries support innovation by providing collaborative spaces, makerspaces, and ICT facilities that stimulate idea generation (IFLA, 2018). In developing contexts, digital literacy programs offered by libraries have enabled users to adopt new technologies to advance social and economic development (Ogundipe, 2021).

Capacity building is fundamental to the growth of knowledge-based economies. Libraries contribute by organising training workshops, digital literacy sessions, and skill acquisition programs. Aregbesola (2022) notes that public libraries in Nigeria have introduced career guidance and vocational training as part of their community outreach, empowering users with employable skills and enhancing local development.

The United Nations recognises libraries as key actors in achieving SDGs, particularly in areas such as quality education (SDG 4), decent work and economic growth (SDG 8), and reduced inequalities (SDG 10). Studies by IFLA (2020) and Oyelude (2021) emphasise the role of libraries in building sustainable communities by bridging the digital divide and promoting inclusive access to knowledge. Public libraries

are uniquely positioned to support sustainable urban development by providing essential resources and fostering informed citizenry. Despite their potential, public libraries in Nigeria face significant challenges. These include inadequate funding, outdated infrastructure, limited ICT facilities, insufficient professional development opportunities, and low public awareness (Ejedafiru, 2020). Such constraints hinder their ability to support entrepreneurship, innovation, and sustainable development effectively. Mansour (2020) found that limited funding and staffing often force libraries to prioritise basic literacy programs over SDG-related initiatives. Similarly, Tbaishat (2021) observed that while libraries can play a pivotal role in promoting SDG awareness, limited community engagement and public understanding of the SDGs reduce the effectiveness of these efforts.

Methodology

The study included all registered public libraries in Nigeria's Northwestern States—Katsina, Kano, Kaduna, Kebbi, Jigawa, Sokoto, and Zamfara—using a descriptive survey and systematic sampling. Three states—Katsina, Kano, and Zamfara—were randomly selected. From these, nine libraries were purposively chosen based on their numbers: three in Katsina, four in Kano, and two in Zamfara. Lists of users and staff were obtained, and 24 users and 24 staff were systematically sampled from each list, totalling 386 respondents. Data collection employed a structured questionnaire focusing on entrepreneurship development, innovation, capacity building, and SDGs. Content validity was ensured through expert consultation, and the instrument was pre-tested outside the study area. Reliability was confirmed using a Pearson correlation ≥ 0.5 . Respondents indicated their agreement on innovative skills using a 4-point scale. Mean scores ranked capacity needs, classifying respondents into high- or low-need groups. Data analysis involved descriptive statistics, Pearson correlation, and t-tests.

Data Presentation and Analysis

Research Question One:

How do public libraries contribute to entrepreneurial development and innovation among users in Northwest Nigeria?

Table 1: Mean Ratings on Public Libraries’ Contributions to Entrepreneurship and Innovation

S/ N	Item	Mean	Std. Dev	Remark
1	Libraries provide access to business information resources	3.95	0.85	agree
2	Libraries organise entrepreneurial workshops and seminars	3.68	0.92	agree
3	Libraries provide ICT tools that support innovation	3.74	0.88	agree
4	Libraries create platforms for idea sharing and networking	3.52	0.95	agree
5	Libraries provide training on business plan development	3.45	1.02	agree
Cluster Mean		3.67		agree

Table 1 shows an average score of 3.67, indicating that respondents generally agree that public libraries significantly contribute to entrepreneurship and innovation in Northwest Nigeria. Among the items, access to business information resources received the highest mean score (3.95), while training on business plan

development scored the lowest (3.45). This suggests that libraries are more active in providing information resources and ICT tools than in offering specialised entrepreneurial training. These findings are in line with Aina (2019), who noted that while libraries offer valuable business information, they often lack structured programmes dedicated to entrepreneurship development.

Research Question Two:

To what extent do public libraries engage in capacity building for knowledge and skill acquisition?

Table 2: Mean Ratings on Public Libraries’ Engagement in Capacity Building

S/ N	Item	Mean	Std. Dev	Remark
1	Libraries provide ICT/digital literacy training	3.88	0.82	agree
2	Libraries support vocational training and workshops	3.62	0.91	agree
3	Libraries organise career guidance and counselling sessions	3.45	1.05	agree
4	Libraries provide access to online courses and e-learning tools	3.71	0.94	agree
5	Libraries enhance lifelong learning opportunities	3.84	0.87	agree
	Cluster Mean	3.70		agree

Table 2 shows a cluster mean of 3.70, indicating a high level of public library engagement in capacity building. Among the items, ICT/digital literacy training received the highest mean score (3.88), while career guidance and counselling sessions received the lowest (3.45). This suggests that libraries prioritise digital skill development, which aligns with Ogundipe (2021), who emphasised that digital literacy is central to capacity-building efforts in Nigerian libraries.

Research Question Three:

What is the impact of public libraries’ initiatives on achieving Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)?

Table 3: Mean Ratings on the Impact of Public Library Initiatives on SDGs

S/N	Item	Mean	Std. Dev	Remark
1	Libraries promote inclusive education	4.02	0.80	agree
2	Libraries provide resources for gender equality	3.58	0.93	agree
3	Libraries empower communities with job-related skills	3.81	0.89	agree
4	Libraries promote reduced inequalities	3.65	0.92	agree
5	Libraries create awareness of climate and the environment	3.42	1.01	agree
	Cluster mean	3.70		agree

Table 3 shows a mean score of 3.70, indicating that public libraries have a significant impact on achieving the SDGs. The highest-rated contribution was promoting inclusive education (mean = 4.02), while the lowest was raising awareness of climate and environmental issues (mean = 3.42). This suggests that libraries are more aligned with educational and economic empowerment goals than with environmental sustainability. These findings support IFLA (2020), which highlighted that libraries’ strongest contributions to the SDGs are in education and equity.

Research Question Four:

What are the challenges hindering public library information services in fostering innovation, enhancing capacity building, and achieving SDGs?

Table 4: Mean Ratings on Challenges Facing Public Library Information Service

S/N	Item	Mean	Std. Dev	Remark
1	Inadequate funding and resources	4.12	0.75	Agree
2	Poor ICT infrastructure	3.98	0.84	Agree
3	Lack of awareness among community members	3.77	0.90	Agree
4	Inadequate staffing and training	3.68	0.95	Agree
4	Policy neglect and poor government support	3.54	1.02	Agree

Table 4 shows that inadequate funding (average = 4.12) and poor ICT infrastructure (average = 3.98) are the most significant barriers to effective library service delivery. Policy neglect and poor government support, although rated lowest (average = 3.54), still constitute notable challenges. These findings support Ejedafiru (2020), who pointed out that chronic underfunding and weak institutional support hinder Nigerian libraries' ability to foster innovation and community development.

Test of Hypotheses

Inferential analysis was performed using Pearson correlation to assess the strength of relationships between key variables—entrepreneurship, innovation, capacity building, and Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Furthermore, regression analysis was utilised to evaluate the predictive capability of library information services on SDG-related outcomes.

Table 5: Pearson Correlation Matrix – Relationship between Library Services and User Outcomes

Variable	Entrepreneurship	Innovation	Capacity Building	SDGs
Entrepreneurship	1.000	0.692**	0.648**	0.615*
Innovation	0.692**	1.00	0.701**	0.655*
Capacity Building	0.648**	0.701**	1.00	0.683*
SDGs	0.615**	0.655**	0.683**	1.000

Note: $p > 0.01$, correlation is significant

Table 5 reveals strong positive correlations among the variables, with correlation coefficients ranging from 0.615 to 0.701. These results indicate that improvements in one area of library services—such as innovation—are significantly associated with enhancements in other areas, including SDG outcomes. This supports the hypothesis that library services are interrelated and collectively contribute to user development.

Table 6: Regression Analysis – Predictive Power of Library Services on SDG Outcomes

Predictor variable	Beta (β)	T-value	Sig.(p)
Entrepreneurship	0.312	5.42	0.000
Innovation	0.278	4.96	0.000
Capacity Building	0.336	6.21	0.000

Model Summary: $R^2 = 0.58$, $F(3,396) = 53.24$, $p < 0.001$

Table 6 indicates that all three predictor variables—entrepreneurship, innovation, and capacity building—significantly forecast the influence of public libraries on SDG-related outcomes. The model accounts for 58% of the variance in SDG impact ($R^2 = 0.58$), with capacity building identified as the most potent predictor ($\beta = 0.336$). This highlights the vital role of capacity building in promoting sustainable development through library services.

Findings and Discussion

The study revealed several key insights:

- Public libraries play a significant role in promoting entrepreneurship by providing access to business information, training programs, and networking opportunities. These services help users develop entrepreneurial ideas and connect with relevant resources.
- Libraries foster innovation by creating collaborative learning environments and offering digital literacy services. Maker spaces, ICT tools, and access to creative content support users in developing innovative solutions.
- Public libraries contribute to skill acquisition and employment opportunities through digital literacy training, vocational workshops, and career guidance programs. These initiatives empower individuals with practical and marketable skills.
- Library services were found to support the achievement of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly in areas such as quality education (SDG 4), gender equality (SDG 5), and decent work and economic growth (SDG 8). However, contributions to environmental awareness (SDG 13) were relatively weak.
- Key challenges identified include inadequate funding, poor ICT infrastructure, insufficient staffing, and limited government support. These constraints hinder the full potential of libraries in driving socio-economic development.

These findings are consistent with existing literature. IFLA (2018) and Oyelude (2021) highlighted that libraries can transform communities when adequately resourced. Nwalo & Oyedokun (2020) emphasised the role of African libraries in reducing barriers to entrepreneurial information. Aregbesola (2022) observed a growing emphasis on digital literacy in Nigerian libraries. Ejedafiru (2020) and IFLA (2018) both stressed resource limitations as major obstacles to library effectiveness. Overall, the study shows that public libraries in Northwest Nigeria play an important role in entrepreneurship, innovation, capacity building, and SDG progress, despite facing systemic challenges. Their strategic contribution to socio-economic development is clear, but greater institutional, financial, and policy support is necessary to maximise their impact.

Conclusion

Public libraries in Northwest Nigeria are uniquely positioned to promote entrepreneurship, encourage innovation, improve capacity building, and contribute significantly to sustainable development. While they face notable challenges, strengthening public library systems through increased funding, ICT integration, staff training, and community participation will greatly improve their effectiveness in driving socio-economic progress across the region.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the study offers the following recommendations:

1. Government and stakeholders should prioritise financial support for public libraries, especially in areas such as ICT infrastructure, resource acquisition, and staff training.
2. Libraries should collaborate with vocational institutions and NGOs to deliver entrepreneurial and digital skill development programs tailored to community needs.
3. National and regional policies should formally recognise libraries as strategic partners in achieving the SDGs and integrate them into development planning.
4. Libraries should initiate awareness campaigns and outreach programs to attract more users to their entrepreneurial and innovation services.
5. Libraries should collaborate with private organisations to expand access to resources, training opportunities, and technological innovations.

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